

Evaluation of constitutive modeling for dynamic plastic-fracture modeling of dual phase (DP590) steel sheets

F. Najafnia^{a,b,*}, H. Talebi-Ghadikolaee^{c,**}, A.H. Bamdad^d, E. Dorchepour^d, R. Hashemi^d

^a Automotive Industries Research & Innovation Center of SAIPA (AIRIC), Tehran, Iran

^b Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Babol Noshirvani University of Technology, Babol, Iran

^c Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of Kashan, Kashan, Iran

^d School of Mechanical Engineering, Iran University of Science and Technology, Tehran, Iran

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the dynamic plastic-fracture behavior of Dual Phase (DP590) steel sheets using various constitutive models. To highlight the significance of calibration procedures, three tension tests—uniaxial, notched, and plane strain tensions—are performed based on stress state analysis. Initially, the Johnson-Cook model is calibrated using a hybrid method. Additionally, phenomenological rate-dependent fracture criteria, including Ayada, normalized Cockroft-Latham, Brozzo, and Rice-Tracey are proposed to characterize both quasi-static and dynamic mechanical behavior. Fracture envelopes are developed for each model based on these tests. The calibrated criteria are implemented into the finite element (FE) code Abaqus/Explicit via user subroutines, and numerical simulations are conducted to evaluate the models' accuracy beyond calibration conditions. Results demonstrate that the choice of calibration test significantly influences the damage value, accuracy of rate-dependent models, and fracture envelope. The notched and uniaxial tension tests emerge as the most effective calibration methods, providing predictions with minimal error. Notched tension is particularly reliable, with the Rice-Tracey model showing an error rate of approximately 2.72 %, followed by the Brozzo criterion at 4.38 %. Uniaxial tension slightly increases the error rate, with Ayada and Brozzo models predicting fracture strains with errors between 5 and 7 %. In contrast, the normalized Cockroft-Latham model shows significant errors at higher stress triaxialities, making it less suitable for precise fracture predictions. Plane strain tension is found to be an inappropriate calibration choice for the proposed simple rate-dependent models. In conclusion, the study recommends the Rice-Tracey model calibrated with notched tension tests for reliable dynamic fracture predictions with minimal testing. If only uniaxial tension tests are available, the Rice-Tracey and Brozzo models are suggested. This approach provides valuable insights for accurately predicting the dynamic fracture behavior of DP590 steel, emphasizing the importance of selecting appropriate calibration methods.

1. Introduction

The automotive landscape is undergoing a profound transformation. Today, they are intricate systems of advanced materials and electronics, engineered to meet stringent environmental regulations and also consumer demands for enhanced performance and safety. This shift is driven by several key factors including consumer expectations, emissions and sustainability, and safety and crashworthiness. In fact, modern consumers demand technologically advanced vehicles, with features that enhance safety, comfort, and performance. Also, Stringent

emissions standards are pushing the industry toward lightweighting [1]. Reducing vehicle weight is not only critical for fuel efficiency but also for mitigating the environmental footprint of automobiles, and finally, Automotive safety standards continue to evolve, placing a premium on vehicle crashworthiness. This necessitates the use of materials that can absorb and dissipate energy during collisions [2].

Within this rapidly changing automotive landscape, steel sheets emerge as a stalwart material, offering a unique combination of strength, ductility, and versatility. These properties have made steel sheets indispensable in the pursuit of automotive excellence.

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* Corresponding author. Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Babol Noshirvani University of Technology, Babol, Iran.

** Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: najafnia.f@airic-ir.com (F. Najafnia), h.talebi.q@kashanu.ac.ir (H. Talebi-Ghadikolaee).

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Understanding how steel sheets behave under static loading is crucial for ensuring the structural integrity of a vehicle during normal operation. However, accidents involve dynamic forces that far exceed the static load. Without a comprehensive understanding of how steel sheets react under dynamic loads, it is impossible to design vehicles that can withstand high-impact collisions and protect passengers effectively [3, 4]. Dynamic testing and characterization are essential for optimizing crumple zones and ensuring that the vehicle structure absorbs and dissipates kinetic energy during a crash [5].

Effective crashworthiness design depends on accurate knowledge of how steel sheets deform, fracture, and absorb energy under dynamic loads [6,7]. Rate-dependent ductile fracture models, calibrated through dynamic characterization, allow engineers to simulate and optimize vehicle performance in crash scenarios [8]. Without this understanding, it would be challenging to design vehicles that meet or exceed stringent crash safety standards. Regarding the important role of sheet metal in the automotive industry and its development, the recognition of material behavior is essential for the selection of appropriate choice and prediction of the structure behavior under various loading. In fact, comprehending the mechanical behavior of steel sheets under both static and dynamic loading conditions is foundational to automotive studies and several studies have been focused on proposing reliable methods for quasi-static and especially dynamic (plastic and fracture behavior) characterization of material using appropriate experimental tests, work hardening, and fracture models.

During large strain deformation of metal sheets, localized plastic deformation (necking) induces a multi-axial stress state, resulting in inaccuracies in material characterization. A reliable stress-strain response of the material after necking up to the onset of fracture can be extrapolated using a suitable plastic constitutive model. To analyze the dynamic behavior of materials, a rate- and temperature-dependent plastic constitutive model, in which flow stress is a function of strain, strain rate, and temperature, should be utilized. Although dynamic loading mainly occurs under adiabatic conditions and is accompanied by thermal softening [9,10], for the strain rate range considered in this study (low and medium strain rates), the condition is assumed to be isothermal. So, the terms in the formulation representing the effects of temperature and thermal softening are excluded.

Viscoplastic models can be categorized into two main categories: physics-based models and phenomenological models. Physics-based models, such as Mecking-Kocks [11], Zerilli-Armstrong [12], Follansbee-Kocks [13], Khan-Liang [14], and Voyiadjis-Abed [15], are mainly founded on thermally-activated dislocation motion [16] to analyze dislocation mobility across various strain rates and temperatures. And phenomenological models, such as Cowper-Symonds (CS) [17], Perzyna [18], Johnson-Cook hardening [19], and Huh-Kang (HK) [20], are formulated based on the additive or multiplicative decomposition of strain and strain rate.

Among physics-based models, the Mechanical Threshold Stress (MTS) model, based on the works of Ulrich Frederick Kocks [11,13,21], has had a significant impact on the field of rate- and temperature-dependent plasticity models. The MTS model has been extensively utilized in numerous studies, covering a wide range of materials, including Tungsten [22], Copper [23], HY100 Steel [24], Tantalum [25], Ti-5553 Titanium alloy [26], 304HCU Austenitic Stainless Steel [27], Cobalt [28], AlMg Aluminum alloy [29], Inconel 718 Nickel-based alloy [30], and High Entropy Alloys (HEAs) [31]. Additionally, it has been applied to various manufacturing processes, such as welded joints [32], machining [33], and additive manufacturing [34]. Recently, Tavares and Meyers [35] focused on the constitutive description of plastic deformation mechanisms, such as the slip-twinning transition, under varying strain rates and temperatures through martensitic transformation. Furthermore, Feng et al. [31] explored integrating the MTS model with crystal plasticity simulations to enhance the precision of material stress-strain response predictions.

Although the MTS is well-studied model for many materials, limited

number of studies in the literature utilized it to predict the rate-dependent stress-strain response of Advanced High Strength Steel (AHSS) sheets. In this context, Dunand and Mohr [36] demonstrated that both the physics-based MTS and the phenomenological JC models can properly and evenly predict the experimentally measured force-displacement curves of Transformation-induced plasticity (TRIP) steel sheet at low (10^{-3} s^{-1}), medium (1 s^{-1}), and high strain rate (10^3 s^{-1}) ranges. In addition, by comparing the loading paths to the onset of fracture obtained from the MTS and JC models, they indicated that even with significant differences in the formulations, the predictions of both models show good agreement with experimental test results. As a sophisticated physics-based model, the MTS model is expected to offer more accurate predictions. However, in some cases, the JC model has been shown to provide equal or even superior accuracy compared to the MTS model. For example, Daridon et al. [37] investigated and compared the effects of various constitutive models, including the MTS, JC, and power law models, on predicting shear band spacing (L_s) for Ti-6Al-4V alloy and HY-100 steel. Their findings indicate that the MTS model provides better predictions for Ti-6Al-4V than other models. It should be noted that for HY-100 steel, the shear band spacing predicted by the power law ($L_s = 0.73 \text{ mm}$), MTS ($L_s = 0.97 \text{ mm}$), and JC ($L_s = 1.01 \text{ mm}$) shows satisfactory agreement with experimental results reported in the literature, particularly those by Nesterenko et al. ($L_s = 1 \text{ mm}$) [38]. In another study, Kotkunde et al. [39] predicted and compared the flow behavior of Ti-6Al-4V alloy sheets under isothermal uniaxial tensile tests, conducted at temperatures ranging from 323 K to 673 K and strain rates between 10^{-2} to 10^{-5} , using four constitutive models: JC, MTS, Fields-Backofen (FB), and Khan-Huang-Liang (KHL). It has been shown that the JC model, with the lowest average absolute error of 3.17 % and a standard deviation of 2.21 %, provides the best prediction of experimental results among the models considered. Additionally, it has been indicated that the MTS model exhibits a higher percentage error at lower warm temperatures (323–423 K). In the different study, Banerjee [40] showed that the MTS and JC models have similar prediction of stress-strain curves for AISI 4340 steel across a wide range of temperatures and strain rates.

While the MTS internal state variable hardening model provides reasonable accuracy across a broad range of materials, manufacturing processes, strain rates, and temperatures, it is important to note that, to the best of our knowledge, rare efforts have been reported in the literature that comprehensively evaluate its performance for AHSS, particularly for Dual Phase (DP) steel sheets. Moreover, despite providing robust fitting results, the MTS model has a greater number of fitting parameters and material constants compared to purely phenomenological models. This requires a more complex testing matrix and calculation procedure. Furthermore, the MTS model is computationally more challenging because it necessitates implementation via a user-subroutine in most FE commercial codes. Additionally, the MTS model has a longer run-time for the same numerical load case. For example, Taylor impact tests with the MTS model take approximately 1.5 times longer to complete compared to those with the JC model [40]. The primary reason the JC model is widely adopted in research, aside from its ease of identification and implementation, is its satisfactory agreement with experimental results under low to medium strain rates, isothermal conditions, and ambient temperatures. Moreover, since the MTS model cannot predict fracture behavior, studies focused on fracture prediction typically prefer phenomenological hardening models, such as the JC model, combined with phenomenological fracture models like JC, Ayada, normalized Cockcroft-Latham, Brozzo, and Rice-Tracey, to enhance adaptability.

In the first stage, it is essential to employ a suitable rate-dependent hardening model to provide the required input for automotive structure modeling. This choice is critical for capturing the material's rate dependency in plastic behavior and for extrapolating results to higher strain levels, as well as for strain rates that might not have been tested

experimentally. Capturing the material behavior of steel sheets, which varies with strain rate, is a complex task. This complexity arises from the intricate microstructural and physical processes that unfold during elongation at higher loading rates. Consequently, the predominant rate-dependent hardening models applied in this context typically exhibit a semi-empirical nature. One example of such a model is the Cowper-Symonds model (CS) [17], which combines two equations. The first equation outlines the evolution of strain hardening, while the second equation accounts for the influence of strain rate. Furthermore, Perzyna's rate-dependent hardening model [18] can be regarded as one of the simplest models that factor in the influence of both strain and strain rate. Additionally, Klopp-Clifton [41] and Batra and Adam [42] have put forth material models that are contingent on the loading rate. Besides the mentioned models, the Johnson-Cook hardening model [19] offers another constitutive equation designed to characterize the von Mises flow stress, relying on factors such as strain, strain rate, and temperature. This approach encompasses three components that account for these properties: The first term aligns with the Ludwik expression [43] and characterizes the stress-strain curve for a reference strain rate. The second term considers strain-rate-dependent hardening, while the final term addresses thermal softening.

Furthermore, there are modified rate-dependent hardening models that have been derived from the Johnson-Cook model, such as the Huh-Kang hardening model (HK) [20]. Several researchers have used the developed mode for the dynamic characterization of sheet metal. In this regard, Majzoobi et al. [44] investigated the dynamic behavior of two low-carbon structural steels, st47 and st52—classified according to the DIN 17100:1980 German standard—as well as an aluminum alloy, using rate-dependent hardening models such as the Johnson–Cook model. In this regard, they utilized the Flying Wedge and Hopkinson bar apparatus for performing the high strain rate test and they determined the material constant of constitutive models using a combined experimental-numerical approach. Zhumagulov et al. [45] conducted a characterization of DP980 steels—designated according to ASTM A1079-17 standard—at different strain rates, including 0.001, 1, 10, 100, and 1000 $\frac{1}{s}$. Their findings revealed that DP980 steels exhibit a moderate level of rate sensitivity. To account for this rate sensitivity and quantitatively assess its impact, they employed modified Johnson-Cook and Cowper-Symonds models, fitting these constitutive models to their experimental data. The results demonstrated that the utilized models effectively capture the material behavior under various loading conditions. Liu et al. [46] employed dynamic biaxial tensile tests to characterize the rate-dependent mechanical behavior of the DP600 steel sheet. They used a Hill48 anisotropic yield criterion and determined the parameters of two strain rate-dependent hardening laws, namely the Voce and Ludwik hardening models. This was achieved through an inverse procedure that relied on Finite Element (FE) modeling of the biaxial tensile test and the experimental data acquired from the biaxial machine, which was equipped with four independent servo-hydraulic actuators.

Also, several studies have been focused on ductile fracture prediction of sheet metal under dynamic loading and high strain rate conditions. Rate-dependent ductile fracture models are essential tools for predicting how materials, like steel sheets, will fracture under different loading rates. These models are designed to capture the intricate interplay between strain rate, stress state, and material behavior during the deformation process. By integrating material properties and loading conditions, these models provide insights into the critical conditions under which ductile fracture will initiate and propagate. Several key parameters and constitutive equations play a central role in rate-dependent ductile fracture models such as strain rate sensitivity and stress triaxiality. To effectively describe and characterize stress states, various quasi-static ductile fracture models like Rice-Tracey [47], Hosford-Coulomb [48], and Mohr-Coulomb [49] incorporate parameters like stress triaxiality and Lode angle into the damage law.

Consequently, numerous fracture models have been proposed to account for different stress states, enabling the determination of fracture behavior across a wide range of stress conditions in quasi-static settings. However, it is crucial to note that ductile fracture in metals is not solely reliant on stress states; it is also influenced by strain rate and temperature. To address this, Johnson and Cook [50] introduced a cumulative-damage fracture model that expresses strain to fracture as a function of strain rate, temperature, and pressure. This criterion has found widespread use in characterizing fracture behavior under high strain rate conditions. Murugesan et al. [51] employed the Johnson-Cook work hardening and failure model to characterize mechanical behavior, including plastic deformation and fracture, under conditions of high strain rate and elevated temperature. In addition to the standard uniaxial tension test, they conducted three supplementary tests to calibrate the rate-dependent hardening and fracture laws. Sun et al. [52] determined the parameters of the Johnson–Cook constitutive and failure models for A508-III steel by conducting a series of tests, including both quasi-static and dynamic tensile tests, as well as fracture tests. Additionally, they assessed the reliability of these model parameters through dynamic fracture tests conducted at different loading rates. Tian et al. [53] conducted a comprehensive study involving a series of tests to characterize the mechanical behavior of Q235 steel. They began with quasi-static tensile tests at room temperature using smooth specimens, through which they obtained the constitutive parameters needed for the Johnson–Cook model. Subsequently, they expanded their testing approach. They performed quasi-static tensile tests on notched specimens and dynamic tensile tests on smooth round bars to gather additional data, specifically related to stress triaxiality and failure strain. This data was then used to fit the failure parameters using the Johnson–Cook damage model, a well-established constitutive model frequently used in high-strain rate applications. The fitting process was accomplished through the least squares method. Also, some modified criteria have been developed through adding strain rate sensitivity terms into fracture criteria which are depends on stress triaxiality and normalized Lode angle parameters, as investigated by Shang et al. [54]. They introduced modifications to the Hosford-Coulomb fracture criteria, taking into account the influence of the strain state on fracture behavior by incorporating a Cowper-Symonds-type rate correction term. Cerik et al. [55] introduced an extended version of the Hosford-Coulomb ductile fracture initiation model that accounts for rate dependence. They incorporated a logarithmic multiplier for strain rates into the model, allowing it to predict ductile fracture initiation in metals under high strain rate conditions. Their approach involved the use of a Johnson-Cook-type hardening model, which included components for strain hardening, rate sensitivity, and thermal softening. Additionally, they employed an associated flow rule. To implement this rate-dependent extension, they developed a user-defined material subroutine. The model's accuracy in predicting fracture behavior was validated through testing on DP590 steel, demonstrating its effectiveness in assessing ductile fracture initiation under varying strain rates. Mohr-Coulomb ductile fracture criterion is another stress state based fracture criterion that can be ingratiated with strain rate terms for developing stress state and strain rate fracture criterion. Xinke et al. [56] employed the combination Lode dependent Modified Mohr–Coulomb fracture criterion and Johnson-Cook criteria for determining the fracture behavior under quasi-static and high strain rates. Also, the rate-dependent form of Lou-Huh fracture criteria was discussed by Xinke et al. [56]. Finally, their results prove that the finite element model using the Mohr–Coulomb fracture criterion predicts the ballistic limit and shear plugging behavior in good accordance with that obtained in the tests.

Previous studies on DP590 steel have often overlooked the impact of calibration tests, stress state, and weighting function on the accuracy of dynamic mechanical characterization. This study addresses this gap by investigating the dynamic plastic-fracture behavior of DP590 sheets, designated in accordance with the ASTM A1079-17 standard. We utilize

various constitutive models, including the Johnson-Cook model, to characterize dynamic mechanical behavior. Additionally, strain rate-dependent fracture criteria are developed based on the Ayada, Brozzo, normalized Cockcroft-Latham, and Rice-Tracey, incorporating the effects of stress triaxiality (η), the Lode parameter (θ), and strain rate on damage evolution. Through a hybrid experimental-numerical approach, different tension tests—uniaxial, plane strain, and notched—are conducted to calibrate these models. The primary objective is to provide a robust dynamic plastic-fracture model for DP590 using simple one-parameter phenomenological models. We specifically examine how fracture criteria and calibration tests influence the accuracy of fracture predictions. To achieve this, we construct fracture loci in the space of equivalent plastic strain, stress triaxiality, and normalized Lode angle parameters, considering the effects of different calibration tests. This research offers a comprehensive and precise dynamic plastic-fracture model for DP590 sheets, highlighting the critical role of calibration methods and fracture criteria in enhancing predictive accuracy.

2. Constitutive modeling and material characterization

The Johnson-Cook constitutive model, based on continuum damage mechanics and viscoplastic mechanics, effectively captures material behaviors such as strain hardening and strain rate hardening [29]. Excluding thermal softening effects, the Johnson-Cook model is described by Eq. (1).

$$\sigma = (A + B\epsilon_p^n)(1 + C \ln \epsilon^*) \quad (1)$$

where A , B , n , and C are the constitutive model parameters. σ is the equivalent flow stress, ϵ_p is the equivalent plastic strain, and ϵ^* is the dimensionless strain rate, which is the ratio of the actual strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon}$) to the reference strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon}_0 = 0.001$). A , B , and n are determined by fitting the quasi-static tensile true stress-strain curve ($\dot{\epsilon} = 0.001$).

At zero equivalent plastic strain, the yield stress and strain rate relationship at room temperature can be obtained from Eq. (2) as follows:

$$\sigma = A(1 + C \ln \epsilon^*) \quad (2)$$

The strain rate hardening parameter C can be obtained from the relationship between yield stress and dimensionless strain rate. To model crack initiation and growth in finite element (FE) calculations, this study employs the element removal technique. Elements are removed from the simulation once their damage indicator reaches unity, as described in Eq. (3).

$$D = \sum \frac{\Delta \epsilon_p}{\epsilon_f} = \int_0^{\epsilon_f} \frac{d\epsilon_p}{\epsilon_f(\eta, \theta, \dot{\epsilon})} \quad (3)$$

In the equation provided, $\Delta \epsilon_p$ represents an increment of the equivalent plastic strain, while ϵ_f denotes the material's fracture strain at the current state and specific stress condition. To characterize the fracture strain, it is essential to establish a fracture locus. The first criterion employed in this study is the widely recognized J-C fracture criterion [22], depicted in Eq. (4). It is important to note that the present study does not consider the effect of temperature.

$$\epsilon_f = (D_1 + D_2 e^{D_3 \times \eta})(1 + D_4 \ln \epsilon^*) \quad (4)$$

The material constants D_1 to D_4 are involved in the equation, where η represents the stress triaxiality. Additionally, the Ayada, Normalized Cockcroft-Latham, Rice-Tracey, and Brozzo fracture criteria are employed as the second type of fracture model to assess the influence of the weighting function on fracture limits and the incorporation of the Lode angle. In this paper, these primary models are coupled with the strain rate effect. The final forms of the phenomenological fracture models, including the normalized Cockcroft-Latham, Rice-Tracey, Ayada, and Brozzo models, are presented in Equation (5) through (8),

Fig. 1. Experimental test, a) tension testing machine, b) uniaxial test sample, c) plane strain tension, d) notched tension.

respectively.

$$\epsilon_f = D_{oh} \left(\frac{3}{3\eta + 2 \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{6}(1 - \bar{\theta})\right)} \right) (1 + D_{oh2} \ln \epsilon^*) \quad (5)$$

$$\epsilon_f = D_{rc} \left(\frac{1}{0.283 \exp(1.5 \eta)} \right) (1 + D_{rc2} \ln \epsilon^*) \quad (6)$$

$$\epsilon_f = D_a \left(\frac{1}{\eta} \right) (1 + D_{a2} \ln \epsilon^*) \quad (7)$$

$$\epsilon_f = \frac{2}{3} + \frac{\eta}{\cos\left(\frac{\pi}{6}(1 - \bar{\theta})\right)} \quad (8)$$

The mentioned models identify fracture initiation when strain and damage values reach a critical threshold. The unknown parameters of these fracture models can be established using experimental and numerical results from calibration tests. Thus, the entire stress-strain and stress state history, encompassing numerical outcomes from the onset of calibration tests to fracture initiation as determined by experiments, should be utilized for fracture model calibration.

Fig. 2. Finite element modeling of tension tests, a) uniaxial tension, b) notched tension, c) plane strain tension.

3. Experiments

In the present study, all tests were conducted on specimens extracted from 1.5 mm thick uncoated cold-rolled dual phase (DP590) steel sheets. Dog-bone-shaped specimens were cut using Electrical Discharge Machining (EDM), with the tensile axis aligned with the sheet rolling direction. DP steel has a body-centered cubic (BCC) crystal structure and consists of a soft ferrite matrix and a hard martensite second phase, providing both high formability and strength. The main alloying element in the as-received DP590 sheet is 0.08 wt% Carbon, together with Mn (1.8 wt%), Si (0.34 wt%), Al (0.034 wt%), Mo (0.03 wt%), P (0.018 wt%) and S (0.007 wt%), as determined using Spark Atomic Emission Spectrometry in accordance with the ASTM E415-21 standard. In all tests, a random black speckle pattern was sprayed onto the white-painted surface of the specimen to measure applied displacements and strain fields using a Digital Image Correlation (DIC) system and commercial correlate software. To explore dynamic plastic-fracture behavior, various tension tests are conducted experimentally at room temperature using a ZWICK universal tensile machine to acquire necessary data. The experimental force-displacement and corresponding stress-strain curves for DP590 are obtained through uniaxial tension tests at different strain rates (0.001, 0.1, 1, 10, and 30). The gauge length for the uniaxial tension tests was set at 15 mm, allowing for strain rates ranging from 0.001 to 30 $\frac{1}{s}$ using cross-head speeds ranging from 0.015 to 450 mm per second on the testing machine. Additionally, notched and plane-strain tension tests were conducted along the rolling direction to investigate fracture behavior under varied stress states. Tests were performed at two speeds (0.015 and 2.5 mm/s) for plane strain and notched tension. Experimental data including force-displacement curves and fracture displacement were obtained to calibrate the stress-state dependence aspect of the fracture model and validate fracture models under higher deformation rates using a hybrid experimental-numerical approach. Illustrations of the tensile samples and experimental equipment are provided in Fig. 1.

4. Finite element modeling

Calibrating dynamic fracture models such as Johnson-Cook, Ayada, Brozzo, Normalized Cockcroft-Latham, and Rice-Tracey requires determining the equivalent plastic strain at fracture displacement. Stress state history during tension tests must also be recorded. To achieve this, tension tests are simulated using the commercial FE code Abaqus/Explicit. Additionally, the validity of proposed fracture models will be assessed at higher tension speeds. The FE model of uniaxial, notched, and plane strain tension tests is depicted in Fig. 2. Samples are fixed on

Fig. 3. The true stress-strain behavior of DP590 at the reference strain rate (0.001 s⁻¹).

Table 1

The strength of DP590 steel at different strain rates.

No.	Velocity ($\frac{mm}{s}$)	Strain Rate ($\frac{1}{s}$)	Rate dependent yield strength/Reference yield strength (A)
1	0.015	0.001	1
2	1.5	0.1	1.021
3	15	1	1.043
4	45	3	1.067
5	150	10	1.050
6	450	30	1.079

Table 2

The parameters of J–C constitutive models for DP 590.

Parameters	A	B	n	C
Value	416	858	0.3976	0.0069

one side, and displacement boundary conditions are applied on the other. The geometry of the FE models was discretized using 3D solid elements C3D8R, with an element size of approximately 0.5 mm in the central region and larger elements in noncritical areas. The element size was determined based on the convergence of fracture strain observed in the uniaxial tension test. Material properties and work hardening behavior are defined as described in Sec. 5. Field variables including the damage indicator, η , and $\bar{\theta}$ are defined in the FE model through a user subroutine VUSDFLD.

5. Results and discussion

5.1. Characterization of dynamic mechanical properties

Ensuring a precise portrayal of the stress–strain relationship is vital for an FE model to accurately forecast the material’s plastic deformation and damage behavior. Hence, this study utilizes the Johnson-Cook rate-dependent hardening law to extend the stress-strain curve. Extracted from experimental findings, the true stress-plastic strain curve for the reference strain rate (0.001) is displayed in Fig. 3. Employing Eq. (1), the curve is adjusted to ascertain the parameters A, B, and n of the Johnson-Cook constitutive model.

The determination of the strain rate hardening parameter C in the second part of the Johnson-Cook model involves establishing a linear relationship between the yield stress and the strain rate ratio ($\dot{\epsilon}^*$). This is achieved through fitting using Eq. (2) to estimate C. Table 1 lists the

Fig. 4. Comparison of experimental and numerical force-displacement curve, a) notched tension test, b) plane strain tension test.

Fig. 5. Stress state during the calibration test, a) uniaxial tension, b) notched tension, c) plane strain tension.

experimental data utilized for this purpose, while Table 2 presents the calibrated parameters, including C, obtained from the analysis.

5.2. Definition of rate dependent fracture models

A combined experimental-numerical approach is utilized to construct a fracture locus specific to DP590 sheet. By analyzing the behavior of three specimens and their critical fracture responses, the dynamic fracture characteristics were elucidated. Comparisons between

Table 3

Stress state and equivalent fracture strain of calibration tests.

Tension test	Average stress triaxiality	Average normalized Lode angle parameter	Equivalent plastic strain
Uniaxial	0.362	0.861	0.538
Plane strain	0.581	0.155	0.362
Notched	0.513	0.438	0.423

load-displacement curves obtained from experiments and simulations are conducted to validate the accuracy of the finite element models. This validation process, illustrated in Fig. 4, confirms the reliability of the numerical simulations by demonstrating a close match between experimental and numerical force-displacement curves for both the plane strain and notched tension tests.

The fracture strain, stress triaxiality and Lode parameter are the three variables to construct the fracture locus. The fracture models considered in this study consist of two parts: one defining fracture behavior based on stress state, and the other determining the strain rate dependency. Each part involves unknown parameters, which necessitate calibration tests for their determination. While the Johnson-Cook dynamic fracture models require at least three tests, the Ayada, Normalized Cockcroft-Latham, Brozzo, and Rice-Tracey models can be calibrated with just one test. The uniaxial tension, plane strain tension, and notched tension tests are employed to calibrate the ductile fracture criteria, aiding in determining the Johnson-Cook parameters and assessing the impact of calibration tests on the accuracy of one-parameter phenomenological dynamic fracture models proposed in this study.

To determine the unknown parameters of dynamic fracture models, it is essential to establish the history of stress triaxiality (η) and normalized Lode angle parameter ($\bar{\theta}$) as functions of equivalent plastic strain (ϵ_p) for each test from the beginning of the process until fracture onset. Fig. 5 illustrates the variation of η and $\bar{\theta}$ with respect to ϵ_p up to the experimentally measured fracture displacement during the considered tension tests.

Because of fluctuations in η and $\bar{\theta}$ throughout the tension tests, it is practical to compute their average values as follows (Eq. (9) and (10)):

$$\eta_{ave} = \frac{1}{\epsilon_p^f} \int_0^{\epsilon_p^f} \eta(\epsilon_p) d\epsilon_p \tag{9}$$

$$\bar{\theta}_{ave} = \frac{1}{\epsilon_p^f} \int_0^{\epsilon_p^f} \bar{\theta}(\epsilon_p) d\epsilon_p \tag{10}$$

ϵ_p^f represents the equivalent plastic strain at fracture displacement. The average stress triaxiality, average normalized Lode angle parameter, and equivalent fracture strain are determined for each test from the results (Table 3). Initially, the Johnson-Cook dynamic failure model has

Table 4
Calibrated parameters of dynamic fracture models.

Fracture model	Calibration test	parameters
Johnson-Cook	Uniaxial tension, plane strain, notched	$D_1 = -5.184$ $D_2 = 5.987$ $D_3 = -0.1417$ $D_4 = -0.01378$
Ayada	Uniaxial tension	$D_a = 0.195$ $D_{a2} = -0.01378$
Ayada	Plane strain tension	$D_a = 0.210$ $D_{a2} = -0.01378$
Ayada	Notched tension	$D_a = 0.217$ $D_{a2} = -0.01378$
Rice-tracey	Uniaxial tension	$D_{rc} = 0.262$ $D_{rc2} = -0.01378$
Rice-tracey	Plane strain tension	$D_{rc} = 0.246$ $D_{rc2} = -0.01378$
Rice-tracey	Notched tension	$D_{rc} = 0.259$ $D_{rc2} = -0.01378$
Normalized cockroft-latham	Uniaxial tension	$D_{oh} = 0.555$ $D_{oh2} = -0.01378$
Normalized cockroft-latham	Plane strain tension	$D_{oh} = 0.415$ $D_{oh2} = -0.01378$
Normalized cockroft-latham	Notched tension	$D_{oh} = 0.482$ $D_{oh2} = -0.01378$
Brozzo	Uniaxial tension	$D_b = 0.556$ $D_{b2} = -0.01378$
Brozzo	Plane strain tension	$D_b = 0.486$ $D_{b2} = -0.01378$
Brozzo	Notched tension	$D_b = 0.511$ $D_{b2} = -0.01378$

three unknown parameters ($D_1 - D_3$), which are defined using curve fitting based on stress state and fracture strain data from three tension tests. Similarly, one-parameter phenomenological dynamic models like Ayada, Brozzo, normalized Cockcroft-Latham, and Rice-Tracey contain a single unknown parameter, determined through a calibration test. Thus, these models undergo calibration using three methods to assess the impact of damage weighting function and calibration tests on fracture limit precision. Following this, the dynamic fracture model's unknown parameters related to stress state dependency ($D_1 - D_3$, D_a , D_{rc} , D_{oh} , and D_b) and rate-dependent parameters (D_4 , D_{a2} , D_{rc2} , D_{oh2} , and D_{b2}) are determined using fracture strain data from uniaxial tension tests at

various strain rates. The equivalent fracture strains for strain rates of 0.001, 0.1, 1, 3, 10, and 30 are 0.538, 0.512, 0.495, 0.468, and 0.459, respectively. Table 4 presents the calibrated parameters of these models.

5.3. Dynamic fracture limit

The fracture limit, depicted as the locus of fracture strains in the ϵ_p versus η space, is illustrated in Fig. 6 for the Johnson-Cook model under both quasi-static and dynamic strain rates.

To gauge the accuracy of the findings, the devised model is integrated into finite element analysis to predict fracture initiation in a plane strain tension test conducted at a higher deformation speed (cross-head speed of 2.5 mm per second) compared to the calibration tests (0.015 mm per second). The fracture displacement in the plane strain tension test at 2.5 mm/s is measured at 2.19 mm, which is then used as a benchmark to evaluate the Johnson-Cook fracture model. Subsequently, the test is simulated using finite element tools, incorporating the fracture model. Plastic equivalent strain versus displacement data is recorded from the numerical model until the moment of fracture occurrence. The comparison between the numerically predicted and experimentally measured fracture displacements in the plane strain tension test with higher deformation rate is utilized to assess the accuracy of the defined dynamic fracture model based on the Johnson-Cook criteria. The results indicate a prediction of fracture onset with an error rate of approximately 6.39 %. These findings are depicted in Fig. 7.

This demonstrates the model's capability to offer reliable outcomes

Fig. 7. Evaluation of the Johnson-Cook dynamic fracture model for a plane strain tension test of DP590 at a displacement speed of 2.5 mm/s.

Fig. 6. Dynamic fracture surface of DP590 predicted using the Johnson-Cook model. Calibration tests include uniaxial tension, plane strain tension, notched tension, and uniaxial tension at various strain rates.

Fig. 8. Comparing the fracture limit of Johnson-Cook and other rate dependent phenomenological models calibrated using uniaxial tension.

for dynamic fracture prediction, rendering it a valuable reference for evaluating the one-parameter phenomenological dynamic fracture criteria proposed in this study. A primary objective of this paper is to identify a suitable weighting function among the one-parameter phenomenological dynamic fracture criteria, which can be calibrated with just one test, along with the calibration test for predicting the dynamic fracture behavior of DP590, instead of relying on the Johnson-Cook model, which necessitates at least three tension tests under various stress states. Utilizing the results presented in Fig. 7, a comparison of the dynamic fracture limits of phenomenological dynamic fracture criteria calibrated using various tests with the Johnson-Cook fracture limit can serve as a guideline to determine the most appropriate one.

Hence, the fracture limit of Ayada, Brozzo, normalized Cockroft-Latham, and Rice-Tracey, calibrated under the uniaxial tension test, is initially determined in the space of ϵ_p and η , as depicted in Fig. 8.

Clearly, the fracture limits are determined for various fracture models (weighting functions) using the uniaxial tension calibration method and compared. The findings indicate that the normalized Cockroft-Latham model does not offer accurate estimations for the fracture limit when calibrated using uniaxial tension. Conversely, the Ayada and Brozzo fracture limits provide relatively suitable approximations, albeit with some differences: Ayada underestimates while Brozzo overestimates the fracture limit compared to Johnson-Cook. It is noteworthy that the Ayada fracture model does not reliably estimate fracture limits for stress states lower than 0.3, whereas the Brozzo model’s results for stress states lower than 0.3 closely match those of Johnson-Cook. Importantly, the Rice-Tracey fracture model calibrated under uniaxial tension yields the most accurate results for fracture limits

among the other one-parameter phenomenological fracture models under the same calibration procedure.

To accurately assess the accuracy and error rate of the fracture limit, the predicted fracture strains by the phenomenological fracture models are compared with those predicted by the Johnson-Cook model across various stress triaxiality values ranging from 0.3 to 0.66, which are the stress states used to calibrate the Johnson-Cook model. The results are depicted in Fig. 9. It is evident that all models exhibit the lowest error in the vicinity of the calibration points, with errors increasing as the stress state moves further away. Particularly, the error of the normalized Cockroft-Latham model significantly escalates in higher stress triaxiality regions, rendering it unsuitable for fracture prediction. The Rice-Tracey fracture model exhibits the lowest error rate, making it one of the most suitable models capable of providing reliable results for the fracture limit of DP590 solely by utilizing uniaxial tension as the calibration method, instead of employing three tests as required by the Johnson-Cook model.

In the subsequent phase, the fracture limits of dynamic phenomenological fracture models calibrated under plane strain tests (for a strain rate of 0.001) are compared with those predicted by the Johnson-Cook dynamic model (Fig. 10). It is evident that the normalized Cockroft-Latham model fails to deliver accurate results when calibrated based on plane strain tension. In this scenario, the fracture limit predicted by the normalized Cockroft-Latham model diverges significantly from the reference value across almost all stress triaxiality ranges. Similarly, the Brozzo rate dependence phenomenological fracture model also exhibits similar inadequacies and fails to provide accurate estimations of the fracture limit. Additionally, although the Ayada model demonstrates

Fig. 10. Comparing the fracture limit of Johnson-Cook and other rate dependent phenomenological models calibrated using plane strain tension.

Fig. 9. The fracture limit prediction error of phenomenological rate dependent fracture models calibrated using uniaxial tension calibration test.

Fig. 11. The fracture limit prediction error of phenomenological rate dependent fracture models calibrated using plane strain tension calibration test.

Fig. 12. Comparing the fracture limit of Johnson-Cook and other rate dependent phenomenological models calibrated using notched tension.

competitive performance with the Johnson-Cook results within the stress triaxiality range higher than 0.3, it still falls short of accuracy when calibrated using plane strain tension. Interestingly, the Rice-Tracey model offers the most accurate results, albeit it remains somewhat inaccurate when calibrated using plane strain tension. Essentially, none of the criteria could yield reliable results when calibrated using plane strain tension tests, indicating that this test is the least suitable for calibrating the developed rate-dependent phenomenological fracture criteria.

To delve into this matter further, the prediction error of the fracture limit is determined across various stress states, as illustrated in Fig. 11. It is evident that the error rate of all models increases significantly when the calibration test shifts from uniaxial tension to plane strain tension. This observation renders the plane strain tension calibration method unsuitable for accurately determining the quasi-static and dynamic fracture limits using the developed rate-dependent phenomenological fracture models.

Lastly, the impact of the notched tension test on the reliability of the rate-dependent phenomenological fracture model is explored. For this purpose, the fracture limit of the Ayada, Brozzo, normalized Cockroft-Latham, and Rice-Tracey models, calibrated under notched tension test conditions, is determined in the space of ϵ_V and η , as depicted in Fig. 12.

In such circumstances, the Ayada, Brozzo, and Rice-Tracey models demonstrate accurate forecasts of fracture limits for stress triaxialities surpassing those within the calibration scope. Nevertheless, for stress triaxialities below this range, disparities emerge among the predicted fracture limits by the rate-dependent phenomenological fracture criteria, signaling their unreliability in these zones. Notably, these findings underscore the Rice-Tracey model’s efficacy in capturing fracture limits when calibrated through the notched tension test, bypassing the necessity for the three calibration tests stipulated by the Johnson-Cook model to delineate stress state dependency regarding fracture strain. Detailed error rates for each model calibrated via the notched tension test are delineated in Fig. 13.

Fig. 13. The fracture limit prediction error of phenomenological rate dependent fracture models calibrated using notched tension calibration test.

Fig. 14. The average error rate of various fracture models and calibration tests.

To evaluate the rate-dependent phenomenological models and the calibration process, the average error rates for each criterion under various calibration procedures are determined and presented in Fig. 14.

It is evident that Ayada and Rice-Tracey emerge as the most dependable models for predicting fracture limits with just one calibration test. Additionally, both notched tension and uniaxial tension prove superior as calibration tests compared to plane strain tension, with uniaxial tension offering a more balanced accuracy in predicted results across stress triaxialities, whether below or above the calibration point. Notched tension calibration yields more consistent results for fracture models, particularly in stress triaxialities exceeding the calibration point. Furthermore, the most precise outcomes are achieved when the Rice-Tracey model is calibrated using notched tension, followed by Rice-Tracey calibrated with uniaxial tension. Brozzo and Ayada, calibrated using notched tension, rank next, respectively, followed by Ayada calibrated under uniaxial tension. In summary, if only the uniaxial tension test is feasible, Rice-Tracey and Ayada rate-dependent phenomenological fracture models are recommended, with the most reliable choice being the Rice-Tracey model calibrated using notched tension. Consequently, the dynamic fracture behavior of DP590 is determined based on the Rice-Tracey and Brozzo model calibrated using notched tension, as illustrated in Fig. 15.

To assess the accuracy of the results, the three most precise dynamic fracture models, namely Johnson-Cook and Rice-Tracey and Brozzo calibrated with notched tension is integrated into finite element analysis. This is aimed at predicting the fracture onset in a plane strain test conducted at a higher cross head speed (higher strain rate) than the calibration tests. The damage indicator versus displacement is captured from the numerical model until the damage reaches unity, with the displacement at this point considered as the numerically predicted

Fig. 15. Strain rate dependent fracture limit based on dynamic Rice-Tracey fracture criteria calibrated under notched tension test.

Fig. 16. Evaluation of the accuracy of the rate dependent fracture models.

fracture displacement in the test. The results of the critical element damage and displacement are depicted in Fig. 16, alongside the experimentally measured fracture displacement in the plane strain test with a cross-head speed of 2.5 mm/s. It is evident from the figure that the models accurately predict the fracture, affirming the reliability of the proposed models for dynamic and quasi-static fracture prediction. The error rate of fracture prediction for Johnson-Cook, Rice-Tracey (notched tension), and Brozzo (notched tension) are equal to 6.39, 9.13, and 6.85 %, respectively.

6. Conclusion

This study comprehensively evaluated the constitutive modeling for dynamic plastic-fracture behavior of DP590 steel sheet, focusing on various fracture criteria and calibration methods. The dynamic plastic-fracture behavior of DP590 steel sheets is investigated using various constitutive models. The significance of calibration procedures is highlighted through a series of tension tests—uniaxial, plane strain, and notched tensions—based on stress state analysis. The Johnson-Cook model is calibrated as a foundational step, revealing the intricate interplay between experimental data and numerical simulations. Additionally, a suite of phenomenological rate-dependent fracture criteria, including Ayada, Brozzo, normalized Cockcroft-Latham, and Rice-Tracey models, is proposed to capture both quasi-static and dynamic mechanical responses. The conclusions drawn from the experimental, numerical, and analytical investigations are summarized as follows:

- The pivotal role of calibration test selection in shaping critical damage values and fracture envelopes, thereby influencing the accuracy of rate-dependent models, is elucidated. Notched and uniaxial tension tests emerge as preeminent calibration methods, yielding predictions with minimal error rates.
- Notably, notched tension calibration exhibits reliability, with the Rice-Tracey model showcasing impressive accuracy (2.72 % error),

followed closely by the Brozzo criterion (4.38 %). While uniaxial tension slightly elevates error rates, Ayada and Brozzo models maintain commendable accuracy levels (5–7 %).

- Conversely, the normalized Cockcroft-Latham model exhibits significant discrepancies at higher stress triaxialities, rendering it less suitable for precise fracture predictions. Plane strain tension is deemed ill-suited for calibration of the proposed simple rate-dependent models.
- Actionable recommendations for practitioners seeking reliable dynamic fracture predictions with minimal testing are provided. The adoption of the Rice-Tracey model calibrated with notched tension tests is advocated as the gold standard, offering unparalleled accuracy and efficiency. In scenarios where only uniaxial tension tests are viable, the Rice-Tracey and Brozzo models emerge as prudent choices, with the former being preferred.
- The normalized Cockcroft-Latham model exhibited significant errors, with average deviations exceeding 14 % (in the best-case scenario), reaching up to 19 %, making it unsuitable for reliable fracture prediction.
- By shedding light on the intricate nuances of dynamic fracture behavior in DP590 steel, the research advances the frontier of predictive modeling, equipping stakeholders with invaluable insights for robust engineering applications.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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